

ETIOLOGY, PATHOLOGY AND SYMPTOMATOLOGY
OF CHRONIC SUPPURATIVE OTITIS.

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The most frequent cause for the existence of a chronic middle ear suppuration is the transformation of an acute suppuration into one of chronicity; however, this chronicity may be induced. The various ways by which this chronicity may be induced are as follows:

1. By neglect of or an inappropriate treatment of the acute stage. This form of chronic suppuration usually responds readily to judiciously applied local treatment.

2. Through the existence of certain types of constitutional invasion that exert an unfavorable influence on local lesions. Such constitutional conditions are scrofula, tuberculosis, syphilis, anemia and marasmus.

3. Through the occurrence of acute suppurative otitis during the invasion of certain of the acute, infectious diseases, as scarlet fever, measles, diphtheria and typhoid fever.

4. The virulence of the infection and the character of the bacilli present.

5. The acute invasion of the attic is very prone to terminate in chronicity.

6. Through local changes excited at the time of the invasion, or those taking place during progress of the case, such as; (a) The development of granulation tissue about the membrane or walls of the tympanic cavity; (b) Through periostitis or caries of ossicles or tympanic wall; (c) Through retention and inspiration of purulent discharge.

- (7) Thorough local changes within nasal and nasopharyngeal cavity.

All forms of chronic suppurative otitis are not secondary to the acute type, as we have a class which is essentially chronic from the moment of its invasion. In this class belong these chronic suppurative otitides due to tuberculosis, anemia and diabetes.

The pathologic changes in the condition under consideration are not limited to the confines of the tympanic cavity, but usually extend from the tube to the mastoid cells and from the labyrinth to the auditory canal, involving to a greater or less extent the between-lying structures. The epithelial structures are markedly altered. There is frequently epithelial denudation and necrosis. In those areas where the epithelium is denuded, we have the development of an active papillary granulation tissue, containing cysts. The mucous membrane is generally infiltrated, and consequently many times increased over its normal thickness. The infiltrate is made up of small round cells, with increase in the number and size of the blood vessels. As a result of the development of the papillary granulation tissue, we have the formation of distinct buds, which, if further projected, form polypi. These are seen projecting from the ossicles, tympanic walls and the periphery of the perforations in the membrane. In uncomplicated cases, the bone is not usually affected. Caries and necrosis of the ossicles are the most common forms of bone lesion in the disease under consideration. On account of its limited nutritive supply, the incus is the ossicle most frequently affected. The invasion of the incus may be in the form of caries of its long process or body, or that of necrosis of these parts, or complete necrosis of the whole bone. The malleus is almost as frequently involved, which may be in the form of caries of the malleus head or the tip of the long process or necrosis of one or both of these parts. The stapes is but rarely affected. As a result of caries affecting the ossicles at the articular surfaces, through the disintegration of the ligaments or the contraction of surrounding fibrous bands, we occasionally have dislocation of the ossicles, most frequently affecting the malleo-incudal joint. The carious process may extend to the walls of the tympanic cavity, especially affecting the tegmen tympani and the outer wall, and that portion of the external wall which is formed by the

auditory plate of the temporal. The inner wall is only rarely affected, such invasion usually occurring in tubercular cases and in those secondary to scarlet fever and diphtheria.

The membrane always presents the external evidences of the changes which have been wrought within the tympanic cavity. There is almost always destruction of the membrane to a greater or less extent. The remnant of the membrane varies according to the degree of the activity of the process. At times, the membrane is congested and infiltrated both in the cuticular and mucous layers; at other times it is opaque from degenerative changes, and showing here and there chalk deposits. Very frequently the cuticular layer extends over the edges of the perforation, thus rendering the perforation permanent. From the continued irritation of the purulent discharge passing through the auditory canal, we have a resulting dermatitis of the canal. The dermatitis produced in the canal is occasionally followed by an atresia of the auditory canal.

The mucous membrane of the eustachian tube is like that of the tympanic cavity, infiltrated. There is an increase in the size of the acinous glands. The epithelia are frequently denuded.

The changes in the mastoid during chronic suppuration are the most important changes which take place in this serious lesion. These changes are:

1. Congestion, swelling and polypoid degeneration of the lining of the antrum and the mastoid cells.
2. Complete obliteration of the antrum and the mastoid cells through granulation-like development of the lining of the antrum and mastoid cells.
3. Osteo-sclerosis of the mastoid.
4. Accumulation of muco-purulent and purulent secretion in antrum and mastoid cells.
5. The formation of cholesteatoma in mastoid.
6. Circumscribed or excessive caries or necrosis of mastoid.

Symptoms.—Frequently the most pronounced and characteristic symptom of chronic suppuration of the middle ear is the presence of a discharge from the ear. The amount and character of this discharge varies not only in the same case at different times, but varies greatly in different cases. The

amount may be so great as to show an almost continuous discharge from the canal, requiring frequent cleansing or changes of cotton, to a fraction of a drop during the twenty-four hours. The discharge may be offensive from want of cleanliness, from caries or necrosis or from cholesteatoma. The discharge may be red, reddish brown, dirty green, or black in color, according as it is mixed with blood, cerumen, epithelial debris or micro-organisms. The discharge may be thick, creamy, mucoid, or watery in character. The discharge may cease entirely for intervals and then recur. Pain is an infrequent symptom in connection with this form of middle ear affection. Pain may be occasioned by an acute exacerbation, by granulations, filling in the perforation, thus preventing free escape of pus, and through the accumulation of purulent discharge in the antrum mastoideum. Caries and necrosis of mastoid and osteosclerosis are accompanied by pain over mastoid and parietal regions.

A frequently recurring head symptom is the feeling of pressure, or actual headache, often a symptom of increased labyrinth pressure or hyperemia of the meninges. Vertigo is occasionally present. Vertigo, with unsteadiness of gait and vomiting, is usually indicative of caries and necrosis, although it may be produced through inter-labyrinth pressure. The most serious case of vertigo, vomiting and total inability to locomote that I ever saw was due to a small growth in the region of the oval window, which was completely relieved by its removal. Subjective noises are occasionally present, but are not so constant as in the adhesive form of catarrh of the middle ear. They are seldom continuous.

Alteration in the sense of taste is also noted as a result of changes in the chorda tympani nerve.

The amount of impairment of the hearing varies greatly, The degree of the impairment of hearing varies also in the individual case at different times and under varying circumstances. The degree of the impairment of the hearing is dependent on the amount of primary injury; on the secondary changes which result through the persistent suppuration; and on sclerotic and degenerative changes. In the individual case the variation in the hearing is dependent upon the weather, the amount of the discharge, the patulous condition of the

Eustachian tube, the greater or less activity of the inflammation in the tympanic cavity, and granulation and adhesive changes about the ossicles and windows. It is frequently noted that individuals hear fairly well as long as there is a moderate discharge, who become quite deaf when the discharge ceases.

The conditions of the membrane and visible portion of the tympanic cavity vary so in this disease that it is almost impossible to give a typical representation of this lesion. The appearances also vary according to the activity or non-activity of the inflammation. The position of the perforation is most frequently the anterior-inferior quadrant, then the posterior and superior quadrant, while frequently the whole membrane is destroyed. The rarer form of perforation is that through Shrapnell's membrane. The form of the perforation also varies greatly. It may be circular, oval, kidney shaped or irregular in outline. The number is subject to only slight variation. One perforation is almost the rule, although we occasionally have two, and very rarely multiple perforations. The size of the perforation varies from that of a pin-hole-like destruction to the loss of every vestige of the membrane.

The appearance of the remaining membrane varies greatly during the active stage. It may have a dull white appearance, due to thickening of the epithelial layer or chalk deposits. The color of the membrane may show also a yellowish red to one of intense congestion. The border of the perforation is usually more highly colored than the remainder of the membrane. The tympanic cavity shown through the perforation gives evidence of varying degrees of congestion and infiltration of the mucous lining. The periphery of the perforation in the membrane may be free or it may be adherent at any one or more points throughout its circumference to the inner tympanic wall; also fibrous bands may be formed between the membrane at the edge of the perforation and the tympanic wall. The long process of the malleus often becomes adherent to the promontorium. As a result of great activity in the mucosa and the formation of villous prolongations from the same, as well as from the result of caries, we occasionally have the development of

granulations or polypi on the tympanic wall; from carious ossicles we have the same result. These growths, when small, manifest themselves as slight elevations from the mucosa, giving off a distinct light reflex; when large they project from the antrum, or attic, into the auditory canal, and can be readily recognized as distinct blood-red tumors which bleed readily when touched. The auditory canal may not only be the seat of a dermatitis from the irritation of the discharge, but there may also develop from its wall granulation masses. Atresia of the auditory canal is also an infrequent condition. In making a diagnosis of chronic suppurative otitis, it is essential that the auditory canal and the tympanic cavity should be freed from all presence of purulent discharge. The cleansing can be made either through the use of the cotton-holder or by the use of mild irrigation. Where the discharge is so limited in quantity as simply to form a hard blackish crust around the perforation and the circumference of the auditory canal, due care should be exercised in the removal of the crusts, as the granulation tissue on which they rest may bleed, and thus prevent a thorough inspection of the disease. The circumference of the perforation, the condition of Shrapnell's membrane, the presence of all or absence of any of the ossicles and the condition of the changes within the tympanic cavity should be noted at this inspection. The region should then be carefully gone over with a probe for the purpose of detecting caries or necrosis.